

Gender Differences in Adjustment Ability among College Students

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The present study aimed to examine gender differences in adjustment ability among college students. The sample consisted of 100 college students (50 males & 50 females) selected through purposive sampling. Adjustment ability was assessed using the *Adjustment Inventory for College Students* developed by Sinha and Singh, which measures home, health, social, emotional, and educational adjustment. Descriptive statistics and the t-test were used for data analysis. The findings revealed significant gender differences in home, health, emotional, educational, and overall adjustment. Female students demonstrated better adjustment than male students, as indicated by lower mean scores. No significant gender difference was observed in social adjustment. The results indicate that gender differences in adjustment among college students are domain-specific rather than uniform. The findings underscore the need for gender-sensitive counselling and support services to promote effective adjustment in college settings.

Keywords: Adjustment ability, gender differences, college students, adjustment inventory for college students

Adjustment is the never-ending journey. Individuals modify their behaviour, thoughts, and emotions in to achieve a balance between personal needs and environmental demands. In psychology, adjustment is widely regarded as a significant indicator of adaptive functioning and overall mental health. Due to increased academic demands, emotional changes, evolving social relationships, and greater responsibilities during college years, adjustment becomes more important. Effective adjustment during this phase contributes significantly to psychological well-being, academic achievement, and healthy social functioning, whereas inadequate adjustment may result in stress, anxiety, depression, behavioural problems, and poor academic performance (Hasan et al., 2019; Babasaheb, 2019).

College students come across various stressors, including academic pressure, examinations, peer competition, and concerns about future careers. For many students, these challenges are intensified by hostel life and separation from family support. The ability to cope with these stressors varies from individual to individual and is affected by different psychological, social, and cultural factors. Gender is one of the most widely researched factors, as males and females often differ in socialization patterns, emotional expression, coping strategies, and societal expectations, especially in the Indian socio-cultural context.

Initial researchers viewed college adjustment as a complex process involving several different areas of a student's life, rather than a single factor. Baker and Siryk (1984) proposed that

adjustment to college consists of academic adjustment, social adjustment, personal-emotional adjustment, and institutional attachment. Previous quantitative reviews suggested that while adjustment strongly predicts student outcomes, gender often show weak and inconsistent direct effects, indicating that gender may influence adjustment indirectly through other psychological processes (Credé & Niehorster, 2012).

Research suggests that females are more likely to use emotion-focused coping strategies and seek social support, whereas males place greater emphasis on problem-focused coping strategies (Compas et al., 2001). While females often report higher perceived stress, they also demonstrate greater emotional awareness and help-seeking behaviour, which may enable social and emotional adjustment. On the other hand, males may report fewer internalizing symptoms but may experience difficulties related to emotional expression and social integration (Matud, 2004; Nolen-Hoeksema, 2012; Addis & Mahalik, 2003; Barrett et al., 2000; Levant, 1992; Wong et al., 2006). These findings suggest that gender-related differences in adjustment are complex and domain specific rather than similar in all areas of adjustment.

Research on adolescent and school adjustment provides important background for understanding adjustment at the college level. Studies indicate that girls commonly display better emotional regulation and social adjustment, while boys show higher levels of expressing behaviours and adjustment difficulties within structured academic environments (Roeser et al., 2000; Essex et al., 2006). Such growing patterns suggest that gender differences reported among college students may reflect long-standing socialization processes rather than situational factors alone.

In the Indian context, studies examining adjustment among college students have reported mixed results. Several research studies reported that female students demonstrate better social and emotional adjustment, mostly attributed to stronger interpersonal orientation and emotional expressiveness (Kaur & Kaur, 2018; Sharma & Sharma, 2017). Other studies, however, suggest that male students show better adjustment in health and educational domains,

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possibly due to greater autonomy and societal encouragement towards independence (Prakash, 2023). At the same time, some Indian studies have found no significant gender differences in overall adjustment, indicating that environmental factors such as family background, residential status, academic support systems, etc., may play a more significant role than gender alone (Boruah, 2018).

Worldwide research reflects similar inconsistencies. While some studies report better social integration and help-seeking behaviour among female students. Other research suggests that gender differences in adjustment are primarily driven by coping strategies and perceived social support, rather than gender itself (Dyson & Renk, 2006). Cross-cultural and longitudinal studies further highlight that self-efficacy, academic preparedness, and social integration are stronger predictors of successful adjustment than gender alone (Larose et al., 2019).

Overall, the existing literature indicates that adjustment is a multidimensional and context-dependent construct. Gender differences, when present, tend to be domain-specific and influenced by cultural, institutional, and psychological factors. The inconsistency of findings, particularly within the Indian context, highlights the need for further empirical research using standardized and culturally sensitive measures. To address these gaps, the present study examines gender-based variations in the adjustment capabilities of college students. This will contribute to a better understanding of adjustment processes in current higher education settings.

Method

This is a cross-sectional study designed to examine the difference between male and female participants in terms of adjustment.

Participants

A sample of 50 female and 50 male students was selected using purposive sampling. Table-1 shows that the mean age of male students was (25.02+3.19) years, and mean age of female students was (23.40+1.30) years. Most of the students were studying in post-graduation. Most subjects were single (male=82%, female=86%) were Hindus (male=96%, female=100%), from nuclear families (male=66%, female=76%) and of middle socio-economic status (male=56%, female=82%), belonging to rural areas (male=70%, female=72%) of Bihar. All subjects were cooperative and gave verbal consent for the study.

Measures

Socio-demographic Data Sheet: To collect information regarding socio-demographic characteristics and other related information of the sample a socio demographic data sheet was developed for the present study.

Adjustment Inventory for College Students (AICS): This inventory was developed by Sinha and Singh (1995). It is intended to assess students' adjustment across five major domains: Home, Health, Social, Emotional, and Educational. The tool consists of 102 items, distributed as follows: 16 items for Home, 15 for Health, 19 for Social, 31 for Emotional, and 21 for Educational adjustment. A student's overall level of adjustment is determined based on the scores obtained in each of these domains. The reliability of the inventory, assessed through test-retest and internal consistency methods, has been reported as $r = .75$. The authors have also reported the inventory to possess satisfactory criterion and construct validity.

Procedure

Participants were selected based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria from different colleges in Bihar. After completing the socio-demographic data sheet, they responded to the Adjustment Inventory for College Students (AICS) under standardized conditions one by one.

Statistical Analysis

The data were analysed using chi-square, mean, SD and t-test. Chi-square was used to find out gender difference in socio-demographic details. Descriptive statistics (like mean & Standard Deviation) were used to summarize the scores on the adjustment inventory by male and female students. Independent samples t-test was done to check if there are significant differences between male and female scores of adjustment inventory.

Results

t-test was used to assess Age difference comparison. It is shown in Table 1a. Chi-square analyses were conducted to examine gender differences across selected socio-demographic variables, including marital status, socio-economic status, religion, social category, family type, habitat, and birth order. The results are presented in Table 1b.

Table 1a

Showing Mean and SD of Participant's Age (Gender Wise)

Variable	Mean	SD	df	t	
Age	Male	25.02	3.19	98	3.32***
	Female	23.40	1.30		

Note. *** $p < .001$

Table 1b

Showing Gender Difference in Other Socio-demographic Details

Variables		Male	Female	df	Chi-square
		Number (%)	Number (%)		
Marital status	Single	41 (82%)	43 (86%)	1	0.298 ^{NS}
	Married	09 (18%)	07 (14%)		
Socio-economic status	Lower	21 (42%)	05 (10%)	2	14.09***
	Middle	28 (56%)	41 (82%)		
	Upper	01 (2%)	04 (8%)		
Religion	Hindu	48 (96%)	50 (100%)	1	2.04 ^{NS}
	Muslim	02 (4%)	00		
Category	General	10 (20%)	24 (48%)	3	9.67*
	OBC	26 (52%)	16 (32%)		
	SC	13 (26%)	08 (16%)		
	ST	01 (2%)	02 (4%)		
Family type	Nuclear	32 (64%)	37 (74%)	1	1.17 ^{NS}
	Joint	18 (36%)	13 (26%)		
Habitat	Rural	35 (70%)	36 (72%)	2	0.09 ^{NS}
	Semi-urban	08 (16%)	08 (16%)		
	Urban	07 (14%)	06 (12%)		
Birth order	First	15 (30%)	11 (22%)	3	6.96 ^{NS}
	Second	18 (36%)	17 (34%)		
	Last	13 (26%)	22 (44%)		
	Single	04 (8%)	00		

Note. * $p < .05$; *** $p < .001$; NS=Not significant

Table 1a clearly shows that there is a significant difference between the two genders in terms of their age. In Table 1b it is obvious that there is no significant gender difference in marital status, ($\chi^2(1) = 0.298, p > .05$), religion ($\chi^2(1) = 2.04, p > .05$), family type ($\chi^2(1) = 1.17, p > .05$), habitat, ($\chi^2(2) = 0.09, p > .05$), and birth order ($\chi^2(3) = 6.96, p > .05$), indicating that the distribution of participants in these socio-demographic area was comparable for males and females.

However, a highly significant gender difference was found for socio-economic status, $\chi^2(2) = 14.09, p < .001$. A larger proportion of males belonged to the lower socio-economic status group, whereas females were more in the middle and upper socio-economic status categories.

A significant gender difference in social category was also found, $\chi^2(3) = 9.67, p < .05$. Females were mostly from General category, while males were mostly from the OBC and SC categories.

Table 2

Gender Differences in Scores on the Adjustment Inventory for College Students

Dimensions of adjustment	Male (N=50)		Female (N=50)		t' (df=98)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Home adjustment	6.04	1.26	5.54	1.16	2.06*
Health adjustment	6.28	1.05	5.78	1.11	2.31*
Social adjustment	7.78	1.39	7.42	1.37	1.30 ^{NS}
Emotional adjustment	13.16	1.87	12.04	1.70	3.14**
Educational adjustment	9.32	1.71	8.66	1.41	2.11*
Overall adjustment	42.58	4.83	39.70	4.14	3.20**

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; NS=Not significant, lower scores on the Adjustment Inventory indicate better adjustment

The results presented in Table 2 reveal gender differences in various dimensions of adjustment among college students.

In the domain of home adjustment, female students ($M = 5.54, SD = 1.16$) obtained lower mean scores than male students ($M = 6.04, SD = 1.26$). The obtained t value (2.06) was statistically significant at the .05 level, indicating that female students were better adjusted than male students in the home adjustment dimension.

In health adjustment, female students ($M = 5.78, SD = 1.11$) scored lower than male students ($M = 6.28, SD = 1.05$). The difference was statistically significant ($t = 2.31, p < .05$), suggesting better health adjustment among female students.

In the area of social adjustment, female students ($M = 7.42, SD = 1.37$) obtained lower mean scores compared to male students ($M = 7.78, SD = 1.39$), but the difference was not statistically significant ($t = 1.30, p > .05$), indicating that male and female students did not differ significantly in social adjustment.

A highly significant gender difference was found in emotional adjustment. Female students ($M = 12.04, SD = 1.70$) showed significantly better emotional adjustment than male students ($M = 13.16, SD = 1.87$), as reflected by the significant t value of 3.14 ($p < .01$).

In the domain of educational adjustment, female students ($M = 8.66, SD = 1.41$) showed significantly better adjustment compared to male students ($M = 9.32, SD = 1.71$). The obtained t value (2.11) was significant at the .05 level.

Female students ($M = 39.70, SD = 4.14$) scored significantly better ($t = 3.20, p < 0.01$) than male students ($M = 42.58, SD = 4.83$),

indicating an obvious gender difference in overall adjustment ability.

Overall, the findings indicate that female college students exhibit significantly better adjustment than male students across most dimensions of adjustment, except social adjustment, where no significant gender difference was observed.

Discussion

The present findings show that female students were significantly better adjusted than male students on home, health, emotional, educational, and overall adjustment measures, with no significant gender difference in social adjustment. This pattern of gender differences being domain-specific rather than uniform is consistent with a substantial body of literature that conceptualizes adjustment as a multidimensional and context-dependent construct (Baker & Siryk, 1984; Credé & Niehorster, 2012; Boruah, 2018).

Several Indian studies report findings consistent with the present results. Comparative investigations of college students have frequently shown that female students exhibit better emotional and social coping and obtain lower (better) scores on various adjustment dimensions. These differences have often been attributed to stronger interpersonal orientation, greater emotional expressiveness, and more frequent help-seeking behaviour among females (Anita, 1994; Kaur & Kaur, 2018; Sharma & Sharma, 2017). The present findings of better adjustment of females in emotional and educational domains support these explanations, as greater emotional awareness and a frequent tendency to seek support may contribute to reduced emotional distress and more effective academic adaptation in the college context (Compas et al., 2001; Babasaheb, 2019).

At the same time, several Indian studies have reported no significant gender differences in overall adjustment, including regional studies conducted in Assam, suggesting that institutional context, family background, and sample characteristics may override gender effects in certain settings (Boruah, 2018). Similarly, hostel-based studies have indicated that female students show higher adjustment problems, especially when separation from family support and concerns related to safety or security increase stress. Gender differences in adjustment are moderated by environmental conditions (Hasan et al., 2019). Mixed findings suggest that gender does not directly determine adjustment; instead, factors like coping styles, social support, and stress levels mediate its impact (Compas et al., 2001; Credé & Niehorster, 2012).

In this study, we found no significant gender differences in social adjustment. This could stem from modern college settings, like mixed-gender classes, more co-curricular involvement, and on-campus counseling. These factors likely ease traditional gender gaps in social integration, fostering similar levels of connectedness for male and female students (Dyson & Renk, 2006; Tinto, 1993). Another possible explanation relates to measurement specificity, as social adjustment subscales may assess behaviours and interpersonal contacts that are now similarly encouraged across genders on many urban campuses, whereas emotional and home-related adjustment remain more sensitive to gendered family expectations and socialization patterns (Baker & Siryk, 1984; Roeser et al., 2000).

In sum, the present study adds to evidence that gender differences in college adjustment are nuanced: women in this sample showed better adjustment across multiple domains except social adjustment,

and this pattern likely reflects an interplay of socialization, coping, and contextual factors documented in both Indian and international research.

Clinical Implications of the Study

The findings of the present study highlight the need for gender-sensitive mental health interventions in college settings. Since female students showed stronger adjustment in most areas, male students could benefit from targeted counselling, skill-building programs and psychoeducational programs. These should emphasize emotional regulation, coping skills, stress management, and help-seeking behaviours. Colleges might reinforce preventive services, like orientation sessions, life-skills workshops, and peer-support groups, to better support emotional and academic adjustment. The even social adjustment across genders reflects strong social integration overall. Still, ongoing efforts are essential to sustain campus environments that nurture overall student well-being.

Limitations and Future Directions

The cross-sectional design of the study limits causal interpretation. The use of a relatively restricted sample in the present study may affect generalizability. Future research should employ longitudinal designs with larger and more diverse samples across institutions and regions. Dependence on self-report measures may tend to response bias. So, future studies should incorporate multiple assessment methods. Future research should also examine mediating variables such as coping strategies, social support, and residential status to better understand gender differences in adjustment among college students.

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